

Channel Marketing in Digital Era

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Abstract

This paper starts with the importance of channel marketing and its types and how it has a relationship with the customers. Channel marketing is a process where the company develops various marketing techniques as well as sales strategies to reach the broadest possible customer base. The goal of channel marketing is to establish direct communication with customers in each channel. The techniques used in each channel is different, but the overall strategy must always brand the business consistently throughout the conversation. Channels of distribution increase the effectiveness of marketing because the middlemen are specialized agencies of delivery. They help to reduce the cost transaction and smoothen the flow of goods and services.

Introduction

The business environment and shopping strategies have gone through significant changes due to digitalization. As for digital shopping, it is an essential tool for any business. It has a promising future for many B2B companies, and many companies have started to adapt their movement towards digital marketing. As for small and medium-size IT companies, it can be read that digital marketing plays a vital role in marketing. After all, IT companies are already working in the technology industry. The new pieces are set by more critical IT systems, for example, GOOGLE, LINKEDIN, FACEBOOK, and AMAZON.

As for digital distribution, it gives new opportunities in providing customers cost-efficient services. And for the digital products, it makes it possible to be available internationally for every customer. As for promotion, digital marketing plays an integral part in the strategy. Online gives endless possibilities and ways to give secure new customers and content. Communication plays a crucial role in online strategy. The messages must be sent and appropriately targeted to attract customers.

Impact of Technology in Marketing

Communication and Technology help businesses grow and prosper, creates a relationship, strengthens the effectiveness of the organization, and allow people to learn about one another. Technologies, mobile phones, such as the internet, social media, and customer's relationship management systems, significantly affect the way businesses communicate with prospective customers. These new forms of information are changing the media landscape and the

type of messaging strategy organization use. Many of the consumers and business professional seek information and connect with more people and businesses from their computers and phones. The work environment is also changing, with more people having a virtual office, texting on their cell phone, or communicating through social media sites such as Facebook, LinkedIn, Pinterest, and Twitter.

Tools of Modern Channel Shopping

Modern marketing uses digital marketing. It could be described as marketing that makes use of electronic devices such as own computers, cellphones, smartphones, squares television sets TV and game consoles to engage with stakeholders. A component of digital purchasing is digital brand engagement. Digital marketing practices technologies or platforms such as websites, email, apps, and social networks. Digital marketing can be through non-internet channel also like TV, radio, SMS, or through internet channel like social media, email ads, banner ads. Social media shopping is a component of digital marketing. Many organizations use a mixture of digital marketing and traditional channel though however, digital marketing is growing more popular with marketers as it allows them to target and track many aspects including their Return of Investment (ROI) more accurately compared to other traditional marketing channels. Digital marketing is the use of a digital channel to promote or market products and services to businesses and customers. A conversion of marketing is underway as we spend more time on our tablets, mobiles, and laptops. The challenge for trademarks is to connect with consumers through all these devices in creating campaigns and real-time that work across social media, e-commerce, and display advertising.

Benefits of Channel Marketing

- 72% of consumers are currently connecting with business through digital marketing channels.
- Digital marketing improves conversions by 24% on average.
- 40% of businesses using digital marketing report “significant savings.”
- The use of digital marketing strategies increases revenue growth by 2.8 times and improves ROI by as much as 300%.
- A cross-functional team should develop the content topics and message priorities that support stated goals. Different use cases and behavior patterns may have different message priorities. So these are scenarios that the team needs to gameplay and test out. Provide space for sub-brand and various units to have their distinctive voices the context of achieving the larger goals.

Advantages of Channel Marketing

Level Playing Field

Any business can contend with any contestant regardless of dimension with a robust digital internet marketing strategy. Furthermore, typically a smaller store would find it challenging to coordinate the grace of the accessories of its larger opponents.

Reduced Cost

It allows the organization to save cash, an element that is taken into account by the organization since digital marketing strategies don’t require a significant amount of financial commitment.

Simple to Measure

Online everything can be calculated. Thus it’s simpler for the organization to know right away if their strategy is operating or not, what organization or customers are enthusiastic about their items, from what places or nations are they, etc.

Brand Development

Existence on the internet can help the growth of the company from any regional market to nationwide and worldwide marketplaces at the same time, providing almost unlimited growth opportunities.

Available 24\7

The World Wide Web never rests and so does online promotions, enabling business with a little source to maintain physical 24-hours parties to contend in the automatic industry using online promotion resources that can run almost 24 hours a day and seven days of a week. So this is also one of the benefits of channel marketing.

Disadvantages of Channel Marketing

Promotion Strategy Can Be Copied

One of the hazards in internet marketing is that a particular system can easily be copied by a rival. And, many have done so with finish ignore for the lawful representation their actions may carry, images or pictures can be used to mislead customers and take away an essential business from you.

Digital Marketing Includes too Many Competitors

Just like the majority of online ads, internet promotion is completed with a great process of too many competitors. Digital promoters are not competent of getting into a more prominent place for the best potential exposure for their promotion and with the use of too many competitors, and promotion tasks will make it even more complicated and expensive to get the internet of targeted viewers.

Lack of Trust

One of the main disadvantages may be a deficiency of believing in of the customers. Because of could be exclusive limited offers that appear to be scammers. So this is a part that declines the picture and trustworthiness of quality and since companies.

Requires More Initial Investment

Playing digital purchasing contains various restrictions like developing delicate and professional looking for your website and planning an effective technique. Therefore, paid marketing like search engines ad words, search engines ads, and social media marketing into quite expensive, especially for small enterprise owners.

Difference Between Traditional and Digital Channel Marketing

Traditional Channel Marketing

Traditional marketing is the conventional modes of marketing that have been made since the beginning of marketing and advertisements. This includes:

- Television, Radio,
- Newspaper, Ads in related weekly magazines.
- Flyers and Letters by the roads and highways.

Digital Channel Marketing

Digital or online marketing is the marketing model of the global village. It is only evident that the era of the internet will have its influence in every realm of life.

Digital channel marketing includes platforms like:

- Social media like Facebook, Twitter, or Instagram.
- Business networking sites like LinkedIn.
- Promotional ads via e-mails.
- Paid pop-ups, Blogs.
- Clickbait links for viral content.
- Pay-Per-click.
- Content marketing.

Channel Type	Examples
Websites	Includes enterprise site, local branches and department sites or pages, micro-sites for specific products or services, sub-brand sites.
Blogs	Separate blogs based on verticals, markets segment, or internal department’s and/or sub-brand.
Newsletters	Segmented in very similar ways as blogs.
E-Mail	Not just a newsletters deliver system, but can provide distinct content through on-boarding sequences, lead nurture and refresher campaigns, and special offers. Also provides a discussion channel for surveys and one-to-one interactions between company personnel and an individual.
Native Advertising/ Sponsored Content	Paid media placement of company content on a third party site, commonly an article or blog post.
Brand Journalism	Combination for both form and approach creating owned media content, but one that takes a more journalistic approach to the content presented, rather than a overt marketing or sales focus.
Video	Ex: YouTube, vimeo, meerkat, periscope, snap chat.
Audio	Ex: iTunes, stitcher, sound cloud.
Landing Pages	Single CTA, one-page site for events, content downloads, newsletter signups.
Visual Content	Ex: Tumblr, Instagram, Pinterest.

Current Trends in Channel Marketing

These are the current trends in channel marketing,

- Artificial intelligence.
- Chabot’s.
- Omnichannel marketing.
- E-mail and marketing automation.
- Voice search.
- Augmented reality or virtual reality etc.,

Conclusion

In conclusion, channel marketing is inseparable from other marketing mixes such as promotion, price, and product. Also, distribution channels help in the control of the product and service flow from the point of production to the ultimate consumers.